

Deliverable 8.2: Communication Kit

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Owner

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is genuinely a result of the Hiperdias project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant

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1 Version History

Version	Summary of Change	Written By	Approver	Date
0.01	Initial draft.	James Clayton	KITE PMs	27/05/2016
0.02	revision	M. Abdou Ahmed	Kite PM's	13.06.2016
0.03	Next Version of Deliverable Report	James Clayton	Kite PM's	08.07.2016

2 Scope:

The HIPERDIAS Communication Kit has been developed in order to promote the effective dissemination of results and findings within the project. This report has been structured in a way that is informative to the Consortium partners and how the communication kit can be used to target all different types of stakeholders.

This document should not be regarded to be a complete or final version. It is intended as a “living” document and as such will evolve throughout the duration of the project. This report will be reviewed by the Consortium and updated in Deliverable 8.5 (M24) and Deliverable 8.8 (M30).

HIPERDIAS dissemination activities will be monitored throughout the project in order to compare outputs against the Dissemination Strategy (which will be highlighted in Deliverable 8.4 & Deliverable 8.7), as well as identifying early potential issues and to comply with European Commission reporting requirements.

The Communication Kit has been prepared by Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd (KITE) with the support of the Consortium Partners. KITE will be responsible for the overall co-ordination of the Communication Kit.

Any feedback on this document should be sent to the following people:

- James Clayton – James@kiteinnovation.com
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3 Introduction

This document is aimed to provide a single point of reference that describes the associated aims and objectives with the Communication Kit and how they will be achieved throughout the lifetime of the project. Much of this information has been designed to continually review and develop the Dissemination Activities for continuous improvement.

The Consortium recognises the importance of communication within a project and has reviewed in detail the Horizon 2020 guidelines on [‘Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants’](#).

4 Aims and Objectives:

The purpose of having 'Aims and Objectives' is to provide direction and a sense of purpose for a project. Without clear 'Aims and Objectives', a project is likely to have inefficient operations. It is difficult for partners to perform in a productive and coordinated manner on a daily/weekly basis without a clear sense of the purpose of their actions. With aims and goals, Work Package leaders are able to delegate different roles to partners in achieving shared objectives.

4.1 Aim

The aim of the HIPERDIAS Communication Kit is *'to provide the necessary tools to effectively disseminate results from the project'*.

4.2 Objectives

The Consortium intentions are to try achieve this overall goal by establishing a number of objectives throughout the life of the Project. For the first six months of the Project, the objectives for the communication kit are listed below:

1. Develop a HIPERDIAS Brochure
2. Develop the 1st Newsletter and circulate to relevant stakeholders
3. Develop future communication tools, depending on the needs of the Consortium.

These primary objectives that have been established for the first six months, will evolve to include key performance indicators by the next Consortium Meeting in September 2016.

5 Communication Kit:

5.1 Communication Kit Research

KITE began by creating a board on PINTEREST on all the items that would need to be included within the HIPERDIAS Communication Kit. This helped the team develop some ideas on the concept and how we could achieve an effective communication kit that was relevant to the project. The HIPERDIAS Communication Kit is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 – HIPERDIAS PINTEREST Board for the Communication Kit.

The HIPERDIAS Project will continue to use PINTEREST, not as a direct social media outlet, but to gather ideas and concepts for future dissemination activities e.g. Video Presentations, Social Media ideas and future Communication Kits.

5.2 Presentation Template

A HIPERDIAS presentation template was created to allow partners to disseminate results effectively about the project, as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 – HIPERDIAS Presentation Template.

This presentation format will be used by all partners to ensure that the Project is being publicised and to also acknowledge the European Commission and Photonics 21.

5.3 Flyer

Printed leaflets and flyers are an inexpensive way of advertising the HIPERDIAS Project to potential stakeholders. The consortium has created a version that provides an overview of the project, as well as its aims, objectives and targets, as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 – HIPERDIAS Flyer (Version 1)

Partners will disseminate the flyers at meetings, Conferences and other activities that could promote the interest of the stakeholders.

5.4 Newsletter Template

A Newsletter Template has been created and will be modified throughout the duration of the Project, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Newsletter Template (Version 0.01) This is an example only

The Project Newsletter will be coordinated on a yearly basis to all relevant stakeholders and will be coordinated by Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd.

6 Future development of the Communication Kit

Partner consultations will take place at the next Consortium Meeting as a means to identify potential ways of improving the Communication Kit. It is acknowledged that successful implementation of the Communication Kit also hinges on the combined efforts of all consortium members.

Partners are to inform the project management team when disseminating any activities in regards to the Project, which might include:

- Project Results
- Attendance of Conferences
- & also images of Partners disseminating their Project Results.

The idea is to gather as much rich data as possible during the lifetime of the project and select the best items to be disseminated.

The management team will continue to remind the Partners of their responsibilities to disseminate and will be informed during the Teleconferences and Consortium Meetings.

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